

Policy Recommendations for Fostering Creative Innovation and Competitive Capacity: A Case Study of Small and Medium Enterprises in Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: Innovation has become a breakthrough and indispensable driving force in the development of science and technology, especially in the country's development plan. Innovation is also the key to boosting the competitiveness and sustainable development of companies.

Objective: The study examines key factors affecting the creativity and competitiveness of Vietnamese small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

Methodology: Qualitative data and interviews were collected from 30 managers across 30 companies. Quantitative data was also collected by questioning 900 managers of 900 SMEs in six major Vietnamese cities. Data were obtained via an online questionnaire and analysed using SPSS 20.0; structural equation modelling was based on Amos.

Result: Research results show five factors (including (1) Financial resources, (2) Human resources, (3) Technology and digital infrastructure, (4) Corporate governance and innovation strategy, (5) Policy and legal environment) affecting the creative innovation and competitive capacity of SMEs in Vietnam, with a significance level of five percent. Additionally, the authors provide five policy recommendations to enhance creative innovation and competitive capacity.

Conclusion: Innovation boosts SME competitiveness. Innovation, technology, and digital infrastructure correlate positively.

Unique Contribution: This study provides empirical data for understanding how to improve creative innovation theory and practice, boosting SMEs' competitiveness and earnings.

Key Recommendation: Creative innovation legislation and policies are needed to enable businesses to become more competitive and contribute value to the community. This allows firms to grasp digital transformation, crucial for promoting innovation, forming new development capacities autonomously, and achieving sustainable development goals.

Keywords: Creative innovation; competitiveness; technology; digital infrastructure; enterprises.

Introduction

In the integration period, highly competitive pressure, economic risks, and the 4.0 industrial revolution have caused businesses, especially group model businesses, to struggle to find and develop markets to meet customer needs (Faeroevik & Maehle, 2022). Innovation is vital to developing competitive advantages and ensuring the company's long-term survival and growth in the ever-changing business environment. Innovation helps small and medium enterprises attract and retain talent, create a dynamic and creative workplace, and promote a culture of learning and creativity, which is ideal for today's young generations (Rădulescu et al., 2023). Thus, innovation helps small and medium-sized firms improve their competitiveness, expand their markets, and recruit talent, thereby boosting their competitiveness and sustainable development.

In today's challenging business market, small and medium enterprises that use innovation to gain competitive advantages and survive and grow are not only a trend but also a key to innovation, flexibility, and outstanding growth. SME growth and survival depend on innovation (Prakasa & Jumani, 2024). Innovation can assist these companies in producing new goods, services, and processes, even from the organisation to the system and market, enhancing productivity, efficiency, and competitiveness.

Innovation is increasingly becoming a major driving force, essential to science and technology development and the national development strategy, the key to rapid and sustainable development. Innovation is here to stay and is the world's development strategy. This is crucial to Vietnam's digital transformation, green transformation, sustainable growth in the new development age, and its development contribution. Science, technology, and innovation in Vietnam are both promising and problematic. The main challenge for Vietnamese companies is technological competitiveness and the inability to fully master advanced technologies like semiconductor chips, AI, and cloud computing (Fang et al., 2022).

Innovation helps SMEs with limited resources focus on areas where they can outperform more prominent competitors. This lets them concentrate on distinctive products and services that better fulfill customer needs. Innovation expands markets and attracts new customers. SMEs can reach new markets and increase revenue and profitability by producing innovative products, services, or processes. Thus, this study sought to identify the factors affecting creative innovation and competitive capacity in Vietnamese small and medium enterprises and propose policy solutions. Therefore, the objectives of the study examine five factors affecting Vietnamese small and medium enterprises' creative innovation and competitive capacity. Five factors are financial resources (FR), human resources (HR), technology and digital infrastructure (TI), corporate governance and innovation strategy (CG), and policy and legal environment (PL).

Literature Review

Creative Innovation (CI)

Innovation is creating or improving products, services, business models, or processes to improve value and operational efficiency. It can come from applying new technology, enhancing operating models, or offering breakthrough solutions to meet market needs (Fang et al., 2022). Innovation

comes in many forms: product, process, business model, and management innovation. This is essential to help businesses improve competitiveness, promote economic growth, and improve quality of life (Ueasangkomsate, 2025). In general, innovation is not just invention but also optimization and upgrading to create superior value.

Competitive Capacity (CC)

Competitive capacity is the ability of a business, industry, or country to maintain and enhance its position in the market through product quality, technology, brand, price, and labor productivity. This is the decisive factor for sustainable development and the ability to survive against competitors. At the enterprise level, competitiveness is demonstrated through the ability to provide superior products/services, reasonable prices, and innovate (Sepúlveda & Collazos, 2023). At the industry level, it depends on technological advantages, human resources, and supporting policies.

Theoretical Framework

Financial Resources (FR) affecting Creative Innovation (CI) and Competitive Capacity (CC)

Financial resources play an essential role in promoting innovation and improving the competitiveness of SMEs. Besides, strong finance helps businesses expand their scale, strengthen marketing strategies, and attract talent, creating an advantage in the market. Businesses with effective financial mobilization and management strategies will be more flexible in adapting to changes in the business environment (Aliasghar et al., 2023). When finances are well managed, businesses maintain stable operations and have the opportunity to continuously innovate and enhance their competitive position in the industry. Therefore, H1 and H2 propose the following Figure 1.

Human Resources (HR) affecting Creative Innovation (CI) and Competitive Capacity (CC)

Human resources play an essential role in promoting innovation and improving the competitiveness of SMEs (Islami & Mulolli, 2024). Businesses focusing on employee training often have higher innovation rates and better work performance. In addition, effective human resource management capabilities help companies attract, retain, and exploit the maximum potential of employees (Asriati et al., 2022). When human resources are combined with appropriate management strategies, businesses develop sustainably and enhance their competitive position in an increasingly fierce market. Therefore, H3 and H4 propose the following Figure 1.

Technology and Digital Infrastructure (TI) affecting Creative Innovation (CI) and Competitive Capacity (CC)

Technology and digital infrastructure play an essential role in promoting innovation and enhancing the competitiveness of SMEs. In addition, strong digital infrastructure helps SMEs expand their markets and improve customer experience through e-commerce and online payments. Businesses that use digital technology can innovate products quickly and create sustainable competitive advantages. In addition, the digital infrastructure helps companies access market information and essential data to build effective business strategies (Lu & Shaharudin, 2024). Thus, H5 and H6 are proposed in Figure 1.

Corporate Governance and Innovation Strategy (CG) affecting Creative Innovation (CI) and Competitive Capacity (CC)

Corporate governance and innovation strategy play an important role in promoting innovation and enhancing the competitiveness of SMEs (Cheng et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2023; Akpan et al., 2022). In addition, a clear innovation strategy helps businesses determine the appropriate direction, focusing on product development, process improvement, and application of new technology to enhance value. In addition, good governance helps businesses flexibly adapt to market changes, reduce risks, and take advantage of development opportunities (Yahaya & Nadarajah, 2023; Chatterjee et al., 2022). Thus, H7 and H8 propose the following: Figure 1.

Policy and Legal Environment (PL) affecting Creative Innovation (CI) and Competitive Capacity (CC)

The policy and legal environment play an essential role in promoting innovation and enhancing the competitiveness of SMEs (Gao et al., 2023; Park & McQuaid, 2023; Zainuri et al., 2024). Furthermore, a stable legal environment provides businesses with confidence to invest in research and development, alleviating concerns about legal risks and sudden policy changes. Protecting intellectual property rights also plays an essential role in promoting innovation, helping businesses protect their inventions and products from copying by competitors (Sabihaini et al., 2024). A favourable policy and legal environment will create conditions for SMES to innovate, improve competitiveness, and develop sustainably. Therefore, hypotheses H9 and H10 are proposed. See Figure 1.

Creative Innovation (CI) affecting Competitive Capacity (CC)

Innovation plays an essential role in improving the competitiveness of SMEs. Innovating products and services help businesses create different values, meet market needs, and improve customer experience. In addition, innovation in production and management processes helps optimise costs, improve performance, and increase profits. Additionally, businesses that apply new technology can enhance their ability to adapt to market changes, mitigate risks, and capitalise on development opportunities (Sepúlveda & Collazos, 2023). Therefore, hypothesis H11 is proposed in Figure 1.

This study model helps identify the influence of essential elements on SMEs' creativity and competitiveness. It also proposes strategies to improve competitive advantages and promote sustainable development.

Source: The authors proposed

Figure 1: The model for critical factors affecting creative innovation and competitive capacity

Figure 1 shows that there are five factors affecting the creative innovation and competitive capacity at SMEs in Vietnam, including (1) Financial resources (FR), (2) Human resources (HR), (3) Technology and digital infrastructure (TI), (4) Corporate governance and innovation strategy (CG), (5) Policy and legal environment (PL).

Research Methods

The authors applied the research process based on 2 stages, including the qualitative and official quantitative stages. These stages are detailed in many steps below.

Source: The authors proposed

Figure 2: The research process for critical factors affecting creative innovation and competitive capacity

Phase 1: The authors create a study model on five factors affecting Vietnamese SME creative innovation and competitiveness. This level involves seven steps: The authors identify the research problem based on five factors affecting creative innovation and competitiveness of Vietnamese small and medium companies. After researching Vietnamese small and medium firms, the writers examined creative innovation and competition. Step 1: The authors focused on scientific and practical themes to research factors affecting Vietnamese small and medium companies' creative innovation and competitive capabilities. Step 2: The authors select study objectives related to five creative innovation and competitive capacity factors. After choosing a topic, the research paper describes its general and specific goals. Step 3: The authors present a study model linked to five characteristics that affect Vietnamese small and medium firms' creative innovation and competitive potential. After setting research objectives, the authors evaluated existing studies on five criteria that affect creative innovation and competitive potential. The authors created a research model after reviewing the research. Step 4: The writers draft a scale after establishing a research model using past surveys and studies. A draft scale uses scales as a framework for qualitative scale development. Table 1 shows the noticeable qualitative results of the questionnaire. Step 5: The author's discussion of the research piece outlines group conversations to capture 30 managers' perspectives. Refer to relevant publications and studies.

The discussions focus on five factors that affect Vietnamese SME creativity and competitiveness. The group discussion will evaluate and expand the first scale to further investigate the study's components. Step 6: The Authors interviewed experts. The authors interviewed 30 managers of 30 small and medium-sized firms using a questionnaire to evaluate the questionnaire and scale after the group discussion. Managerial directors at SMEs are being interviewed. Expert interviews are aimed at confirming the scale's quality before it is used for data collection and quantitative research. This stage concluded the theoretical research survey. Results from the November 2024 to January 2025 poll have been processed. The authors used a structural equation model (SEM) to evaluate the model and research hypotheses following scale reliability testing and factor analysis. **Phase 2:** The writers conducted an official survey, analysed data, arrived at conclusions, and made managerial recommendations. Step 7: The Authors conducted a formal survey: The authors submitted survey questionnaires to 900 small and medium business managers in six major Vietnamese cities: Can Tho, Ho Chi Minh, Da Nang, Hai Phong, Hue, and Ha Noi. We expect to distribute 900 ballots to ensure that quantitative research has enough observations. Remotely mailing questionnaires using docs.google.com was used to survey six centrally administered cities. Hair et al. (2018) found the following degrees of agreement: (1) severely disagree, (2) disagree, (3) neutral, (4) agree, (5) strongly agree. Each participant received a handy sampling process. The 835 samples analyzed yielded 65 incomplete votes. Thus, the study model used just 835 votes. Step 8: Authors analyzed the data: The significant survey data will be put into SPSS 20.0 for descriptive statistics and Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient tests: Tests for Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient assessed measuring scale reliability. This was crucial for verifying construct internal coherence and survey questions assessing theoretical variables. We changed or deleted low-reliability elements to make the measurement model more robust; 0.7 was considered satisfactory for scale reliability. The measurement model was developed by identifying key latent components and studying the observed variables' underlying structure using exploratory factor analysis (EFA). This followed reliability testing. The dataset was tested for factor analysis using Bartlett's sphericity test and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test. Our statistical cutoffs for retention were eigenvalues above 1.0 and factor loadings over 0.5. Due to this technique, the last factors represented the researched constructions well. The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) will use Amos software. The confirmatory factor analysis was done with Amos. The degree to which items within a construct are connected and the degree to which constructs are distinct could be assessed using CFA for construct validity. The model's effectiveness was evaluated using well-known goodness-of-fit metrics, such as CFI (>0.8), TLI (>0.9), RMSEA (<0.08), and χ^2/df ratio (χ^2/df). Adjustments improved model fit and theoretical consistency. The authors had conclusions and provided managerial implications.

Study Results

Table 1 helped understand SMEs' innovation, competition, and external environmental factors, laying the groundwork below.

Table 1: Testing descriptive statistics and Cronbach's alpha for critical factors influencing the creative innovation and competitive capacity

Items and code	Cronbach's alpha	Mean
1. Financial resources (FR: FR1, FR2, FR3, FR4)	0.960	3.076
2. Human resources (HR: HR1, HR2, HR3, HR4)	0.853	3.432
3. Technology and digital infrastructure (TI: TI1, TI2, TI3, TI4)	0.964	3.075
4. Corporate governance and innovation strategy (CG: CG1, CG2, CG3, CG4)	0.955	3.066
5. Policy and legal environment (PL: PL1, PL2, PL3, PL4)	0.868	2.426
6. Creative innovation (CI: CI1, CI2, CI3)	0.957	3.402
7. Competitive capacity (CC: CC1, CC2, CC3, CC4)	0.872	2.393

Source: Processing from SPSS 20.0

Table 1 presents descriptive data and Cronbach's alpha coefficients (greater than 0.6) for the main characteristics influencing creative innovation and competitive capacity. The analysis investigates the constructs' internal consistency and offers information on individual items' mean values and standard deviations. The results highlight the importance of financial flexibility, technical advancement, and supporting regulatory frameworks in encouraging creative innovation and competitiveness. While businesses actively engage in innovation, resolving financial, infrastructure, and policy shortages could improve their capacity to maintain a competitive advantage. These findings have important implications for business executives and politicians working to boost the innovation ecosystem.

Source: Processing from SPSS 20.0, Amos

Figure 3: The SEM testing for critical factors affecting the creative innovation and competitive capacity

Figure 3 presents SEM results showing causal relationships between key creative innovation and competitive capability components. Model fit indices ($\chi^2/df < 5.0$, CFI > 0.80, TLI > 0.90, RMSEA < 0.08) indicate adequate model performance. Financial resources ($\beta > 0.30$, $p < 0.05$), human

resources ($\beta > 0.40$, $p < 0.01$), and technological infrastructure ($\beta > 0.35$, $p < 0.01$) positively affect creativity. Corporate governance ($\beta > 0.25$, $p < 0.05$) boosts innovation, while policy and legal issues ($\beta < 0.20$, $p > 0.05$) have less impact. Creative innovation (CI) enhances competitiveness ($\beta > 0.50$, $p < 0.01$) and impacts resource allocation. Businesses should prioritize financial sustainability, technology adoption, and talent development. Innovation requires stronger regulatory frameworks from policymakers. Strategic digital transformation and R&D investments boost competitiveness. Good corporate governance fosters long-term innovation-driven growth and supports multidimensional innovation for sustainable company strategy.

Table 2: Relationships testing key factors affecting the creative innovation and competitive capacity

Relationships	Standardized estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Result
HR → CI	0.145	0.031	4.581	***	Accepted H3
PL → CI	0.089	0.054	3.055	0.002	Accepted H9
TI → CI	0.573	0.028	18.765	***	Accepted H5
CG → CI	0.096	0.023	3.399	***	Accepted H7
FR → CI	0.107	0.024	3.745	***	Accepted H1
CI → CC	0.289	0.028	7.330	***	Accepted H11
FR → CC	0.123	0.018	4.098	***	Accepted H2
CG → CC	0.086	0.017	2.985	0.003	Accepted H8
TI → CC	0.350	0.025	9.192	***	Accepted H6
PL → CC	0.160	0.041	5.174	***	Accepted H10
HR → CC	0.130	0.022	3.986	***	Accepted H4

Note: *** is significance 0.01; processing from SPSS 20.0, Amos

Table 2 outlines five factors affecting creative innovation and competitiveness in Vietnamese SMEs based on the 0.05 significance level applied to these variables. The essay identifies technology and digital infrastructure (TI) as a factor that affects Vietnam's SMES' creative innovation and competitiveness. Standardized estimates of this impact are 0.573. This is the most critical factor and policy priority, with significant consequences. Small and medium firms in Vietnam are behind developed nations in digital technologies and automation.

Table 3: Factors affecting the creative innovation and competitive capacity based on testing average variance extracted

Indicators	CR	AVE	MSV	Results
HR	0.825	0.549	0.052	Good
TI	0.965	0.872	0.387	Good
FR	0.950	0.826	0.052	Good
CG	0.952	0.833	0.021	Good
CC	0.872	0.634	0.286	Good

PL	0.867	0.630	0.046	Good
CI	0.949	0.860	0.387	Good

Source: Processing from SPSS 20.0, Amos

Table 3 shows the construct reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE), and maximum shared variance (MSV) of essential components affecting creative innovation (CI) and competitive capacity. The results reveal that all conceptions meet the validity and reliability requirements, indicating robust measures. Some countries have effectively implemented many policy measures to boost business capacity and innovation, which promotes technology adoption. The results showed the bootstrap results for the relationships between human resources (HR), financial resources (FR), technology and digital infrastructure (TI), Corporate governance and innovation strategy (CG), policy and legal environment (PL), creative innovation (CI), and competitive capacity. Prioritise technology and digital infrastructure to boost innovation and competitiveness.

Discussion of Findings

SEM testing identified five significant characteristics that affect creative innovation and competitive capacity in small and medium-sized firms, with a significance level of 0.05. The SEM model's structural path coefficients examined the relationships between financial resources (FR), human resources (HR), technology and digital infrastructure (TI), corporate governance and innovation strategy (CG), policy and legal environment (PL), creative innovation (CI), and competitive capacity. Synchronised author discussions include:

(1) Model validation and significance: The H1-H11 hypotheses were accepted, with C.R. values above 1.96, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Strong route coefficients support the conceptual framework, emphasising resource allocation, innovation, and competitiveness (Aliasghar et al., 2023; Islami & Mulolli, 2024). Therefore, strengthening the legal corridor and intellectual property protection tools is necessary to create a healthy competitive environment and motivate innovation. The state should have a tax exemption policy for small and medium enterprises in the early years of start-up to help them have better resources for business and innovation. The state needs to look more closely at the issue of copyright and copyright infringement.

(2) Technology and digital infrastructure ($TI \rightarrow CI, \beta = 0.573, p < 0.001$) is the primary driver of creative innovation (CI), highlighting the significance of digital transformation. FR and HR significantly impact innovation, emphasising the need for consistent finance and skilled personnel ($FR \rightarrow CI, \beta = 0.107, p < 0.001$). Innovation is less affected by corporate governance ($CG \rightarrow CI, \beta = 0.096, p < 0.001$) and policy and legal environment ($PL \rightarrow CI, \beta = 0.089, p = 0.002$). Strategic leadership and regulatory backing promote innovation, but technology and financial investments have a more significant impact (Lu & Shaharudin, 2024; Cheng et al., 2023). Therefore, training human resources with innovative thinking early on is vital for forming a culture of innovation in all individuals and organisations. Hence, the education system needs to be innovated, bringing innovation into early education from high school levels, creating community playgrounds and funds to promote innovation, and increasing experimental and experiential activities to increase students' innovative thinking ability.

(3) Creative innovation (CI → CC, $\beta = 0.289$, $p < 0.001$) improves competitiveness by balancing the impact of innovation on resources and advantage. Technology Infrastructure (TI → CC, $\beta = 0.350$, $p < 0.001$) remains a major predictor, emphasising the importance of digital capabilities for competitive success. Financial stability and skilled labor enhance firms' market positioning (FR → CC, $\beta = 0.123$, $p < 0.001$) and competitiveness (HR → CC, $\beta = 0.130$, $p < 0.001$). Policy and legal environment (PL → CC, $\beta = 0.160$, $p < 0.001$) moderately impact firms, suggesting positive regulatory frameworks improve competitiveness. Despite being statistically significant, Corporate Governance has the least impact on competitiveness (CG → CC, $\beta = 0.086$, $p = 0.003$). Governance promotes strategic innovation, although its direct effect is weaker (Kumar et al., 2023; Akpan et al., 2022; Gao et al., 2023).

(4) Creative innovation mediates the links between FR, HR, TI, CG, PL, and CC, emphasising the need for innovation-driven methods to turn resources into competitive advantages. Technology infrastructure benefits most indirectly since it spurs innovation and competitiveness. Thus, the state must establish playgrounds, forums, incubators, ecosystems, and tools to promote knowledge sharing. This is crucial for creative applications and competitiveness. State backing has eluded many small and medium firms. Their lack of knowledge, information, experience, and cash will be hard to overcome if left to struggle. Forum networks enable small and medium firms to mature in expertise and resources quickly.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

Based on a poll of 900 managers from 900 SMEs in six major Vietnamese cities, many notable findings emerged from a review of creative innovation and competitive capacity components. Technology and digital infrastructure have a significant impact on both creative innovation and competitive capacity, emphasising the importance of digital transformation for achieving a competitive advantage. Innovation requires consistent finance and innovative individuals from financial and human resources. Corporate governance and innovation strategy indirectly promote innovation through strategic leadership. The policy and legal environment also play a role in encouraging innovation, although not exclusively. Creative innovation connects resources and competitiveness, emphasising its importance in turning investments into long-term benefits. The findings underscore the need to promote innovation through technology, finance, human resources, and governance.

Recommendations

Based on model testing, the authors proposed the following policy recommendations:

(1) Prioritise technology and digital infrastructure: Businesses should invest in more in-depth research on innovation, application, and development of new information technologies, such as internet networks, secure data storage systems, and flexible cloud computing services. They should devise innovative projects that are suitable for practical application, with high feasibility to achieve results when implemented. In addition, the state needs to increase investment and improve infrastructure for science, technology, innovation, and national digital transformation. In particular, allocate the state budget for scientific research to serve strategic technology research and promulgate public-private cooperation mechanisms and policies for strategic technology

research and development. There are mechanisms and policies to support and encourage organisations, individuals, and businesses to invest and build laboratories and centres for research and development of science and technology.

(2) Providing stable financial resources and skilled personnel will promote long-term innovation initiatives and cultivate creative talent in the workforce. Leaders must be determined to shift their thinking and set innovation goals. Encourage employees to learn and develop new skills to innovate and adapt to business changes, be willing to listen, collaborate, and communicate effectively between departments and work groups to promote idea-sharing and creativity. Search for investment sources, policies, and opportunities to access new technological knowledge through cooperative relationships and interactions within the network, especially interactive relationships with foreign partners to incorporate into businesses. Business administrators must proactively seek external financial resources such as government financial support packages and tax incentive policies for business organisations that research and develop in the direction of innovation.

(3) Strengthen corporate governance by encouraging companies to foster employee innovation and experiment with new working methods. Additionally, the state should vigorously promote science, technology, innovation, and digital transformation activities in businesses. In particular, preferential policies encourage companies, especially small and medium enterprises, to invest in digital transformation, research, scientific application, and technological innovation to improve production business efficiency and corporate governance. Promote the consumption of products and services in the digital environment, ensuring that the digital economy of industries and fields accounts for at least 70% of the digital economy. Promote innovative production in industries and fields: Agriculture, trade, finance, education, health, transportation, logistics.

(4) Improve policy support by establishing organisations, capital support funds, and credit guarantee funds, creating more opportunities for SMES to access capital. Enhancing SMES' scientific and technology capacity and improving government and state management agency support in the capital, mechanisms, policies, laws, trade promotion, education, and training. Modern business equipment, technology consulting, and State policies must construct science-technology market-building institutions. This also boosts the role of associations, clubs, director clubs, and professional and technical groups in business development. Improve the investment and business environment and promote administrative procedure reform to create maximum convenience for SMEs to participate in production and business.

(5) Businesses should foster a creative culture, respect intellectual property rights, simplify administrative processes, and increase transparency and information accessibility. Develop business human resources to satisfy technological innovation, production, and business process needs and participate in the global business chain by diversifying high-quality products and international services. Enhance training, development, and fostering of business human resources to meet business development needs by equipping them with new knowledge and skills in technical expertise, professions, information technology, foreign languages, and business situations, following regional and international education and training standards.

Limitations and future research: This study's cross-sectional design, industry-specific focus, and potential measurement biases limit its ability to generalize across sectors. Longitudinal research could reveal how innovation methods change over time. Future studies should focus on AI-driven innovation, policy efficacy, and industry-specific trends. Comparative studies of developed and emerging markets could provide more detailed insights into institutional implications on innovation. ESG issues may play a more prominent role in long-term corporate competitiveness. Expanding datasets and adding external macroeconomic variables will increase research validity.

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